

Individualized and personalized support system for students' reading, mathematical and scientific literacy development

Version 0

Description

Empirical data collected during the study that describes the findings.

Focus group discussions, expert interviews, lesson observation and workshop notes and data sets, versions of conceptual models ect.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Individualized and personalized support system for students' reading, mathematical and scientific literacy development

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia, Interdisciplinary Centre for Educational
Innovation

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Individualized and personalized support system for students' reading, mathematical and scientific literacy development

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Organizations:

University of Latvia, Interdisciplinary Centre for Educational Innovation

Contact: Girts Burgmanis

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Individualized and personalized support system for students' reading, mathematical and scientific literacy development

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-06-07

4. Templates

Descriptions

Empirical data collected during the study that describes the findings

To follow-up of the data on focus groups, workshops, expert interviews, surveys, lesson observations and decisions during the project. To access the detailed information of numerical and textual data.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data will be collected to achieve three objectives of project: a) to develop and improve conceptual model and a descriptive framework of a multi-tiered system of support for differentiated, personalized and inclusive T&L in diverse classrooms; b) to develop recommendations for education policymakers, experts, and educators on implementing multi-tiered system of support in diverse classrooms; c) to develop and improve students learning progress diagnostic toolkit including theoretical and research-based learning and assessment framework for development of TSs to support 3FLs learning of students aged 5 to 16.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Experimental data
- Textual data
- Observation data
- Other

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- txt
- pdf
- csv
- png
- xls
- jpg

1.1.4 Expected size of the data - give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

students, researchers, policy makers

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

focus group discussions, expert interviews, lesson observation transcripts, conceptual models

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Access will be granted upon receiving a concrete proposal for a scientific collaboration, as well as the purpose of re-using this dataset.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Data will be accessible only after the project has ended to ensure that the ownership of products and applied solutions is secured.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any software which can open and read rich text and csv format files.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?
Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-22

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2031-12-21

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Girts Burgmanis (orcid:0000-0001-5903-2283)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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